

The Dynamics of Fishermen's Organizations: Formations and Movement Against Prohibition of Large-net Usage Policy in Indonesia

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Abstract:

This paper intends to analyze and explain the dynamics of fishermen's organizations, particularly regarding their formations and movements against the prohibition of large-net (*payang*) usage policy in the Lamongan Regency. The reason large-net (*payang*) is not authorized as a fishing gear is that it is considered an not environmental friendly fishing gear that has resulted in the decline of the fish population. This policy then caused resistance from the fishing community in coastal Lamongan. The method used is qualitative, with a case study approach. Data was collected through several techniques, namely, literature review, observation, and in-depth interviews. The results showed that the movement was carried out by involving various organizations that had been previously formed independently with driving actors who had long been involved in fishermen's organizations. Furthermore, the movement was deemed successful with the issuance of a presidential instruction that provided a moratorium on the policy of prohibition of large-net (*payang*).

Keywords: *fishermen, organizations, formation, movement.*

Introduction

The social characteristics of coastal communities differ from agrarian communities, where agricultural communities have controlled resources, namely land management for producing a commodity. Meanwhile, fishermen are still open access because people often move around to get maximum results (Satria, 2015).

This kind of condition then causes fishermen to have hard, firm, and open characteristics. In addition to characteristics, fishing communities also have a specific cultural identity and are formed through a long process. The characteristics of the fisherman's identity include the gender system, patron-client relations, behavioral patterns in exploiting fishery resources, and social leadership that grows due

to the influence of conditions and characteristics found in the surrounding environment (Wijaya, 2016). The ability of coastal communities to adapt and respond to the challenges of social change affects and determines the survival and social integration of fishing communities (Kusnadi, 2014).

The organization is a goal-oriented social entity designed in a structured and coordinated manner as a system with a relationship with the external environment (Daft et al., 2020). Furthermore, according to Robins (2019), an organization is a social unit that is consciously coordinated by a group of people (consisting of two or more people), who work together continuously to achieve a common goal. This conscious organization is an action taken by individuals who direct each other - directed so that there is no miscommunication in understanding the main task given. Then, the most important conceptually the organization is a forum that can be used to coordinate a joint action for predetermined goals (Jones, 2013). These goals are reduced to targets that must be achieved by individuals so that the organization can continue to grow and good cooperation between individuals is needed to achieve the goals that have been set. This is in line with the opinion of McShane & Von Glinow (2015) who states that an organization is a group of interdependent people working together to achieve predetermined goals.

At first, small social groups were formed as a place to interact with each other. Over time, in dealing with complex life, humans are directed to institutionalize these small groups in the form of an organization where there is an arrangement/structure with a mechanism for dividing tasks between each member. Fishermen need organizations to accommodate all needs related to the lives of fishermen based on various considerations and carried out together to achieve common goals. So that not a few fishermen form social units (social groupings) as a forum for exchanging ideas to achieve common goals.

A fisher organization is a group or entity involved in fishing activities, which may include

commercial, recreational, or subsistence fishing. Rakhmanda et. al. (2018) defined fisher organizations as a manifestation of collective consciousness about community identity that depends on the economic activities of capture fisheries in the region (Rakhmanda, Suadi, & Djasmani, 2018). Fisher organizations can take many forms, such as cooperatives, associations, or companies. Some fisher organizations focus on a specific type of fish fishery, such as tuna (Bez et al., 2011). Others may focus on managing fishermen's activities in a specific region or on the high seas (Auster et al., 2011).

In general, fisheries operations are managed by various fisheries institutions consisting of the state, corporations or companies, groups, and individuals (Rakhmanda, Suadi, & Djasmani, 2018). Fishing companies are organizations or business entities involved in fishing activities and trading of fish catches. They operate in the commercial fisheries sector intending to make a profit through fishing and selling the catch. In addition, there are Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs) abroad as an important role in the implementation of international cooperation and conservation and management obligations set by the United Nations (Rosello, 2022). The United Nations also has the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO). FAO is an international organization that aims to reduce the fishing capacity of fishermen (Fare et al., 2000). FAO's goal is to develop methods to calculate fishing capacity and reduce capacity at the national level, both short and long-term.

This research was conducted in Lamongan Regency, East Java. The area of Lamongan Regency has an area of 1,812.8 km² or occupies about 3.73% of the total area of East Java Province. Administratively, Lamongan Regency consists of 27 sub-districts, which include 462 villages, 12 sub-districts, and 1,431 hamlets. Lamongan Regency is geographically located at coordinates 112° 33' – 112° 34' east longitude and 6° 51' – 7° 23' south latitude, of the 27 sub-districts, Lamongan Regency only has two coastal districts. The two sub-districts are Paciran and Brondong districts. The length of the coastline of Lamongan Regency reaches

35,507 km. In general, the people of Lamongan Regency work as farmers because the topography of Lamongan Regency is almost 72.5% which is lowland with a slope of 0-2%.

However, work as a fisherman still dominates with around 18,836 people working as fishermen while 10,976 people have non-fishing jobs.

Figure 1. Nusantara Fishing Port, Brondong.

Source: Researcher Documentation.

The fishery sector is a leading commodity in Lamongan Regency, especially in Brondong District. There are five Fish Auction Places/FAP (*Tempat Pelelangan Ikan* or TPI) and one *Nusantara* (National) Fishing Port NFP Brondong (*Pelabuhan Perikanan Nusantara* or PPN), which is a location that accommodates fish sales activities caught by fishermen in Brondong District. In 2016 the total fish production reached around 66,993,831 tons and *Minatani* Fish Auction Places / Brondong Fish Auction Places were the most fish sales locations in Brondong District, which reached around 66,178,997 tons in 2016. There is more large-net (*payang*) fishermen than using other fishing gear. Fishing Port Brondong as the largest port in Lamongan Regency is dominated by large-net (*payang*) fishermen, so it is not surprising that loading and unloading occur every day at that place. In addition, large-net (*payang*) fishermen assume that other fishing gear does not provide more profitable results than large-net (*payang*) fishing gear, so they are reluctant to change their

fishing gear as instructed by the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries.

Large-net (*payang*) is a fishing gear used by fishermen for active fishing. The method of operation is by spreading a sheet rope in a circle, followed by lowering the large-net (*payang*), and then the two ends of the sheet rope are brought together and pulled towards the ship until the entire bag is lifted. Actually, large-net (*payang*) fishing gear is an environmentally friendly fishing gear. In fact, the government once allowed this fishing gear to be used legally through Presidential Decree No. 39 of 1980. However, the currently banned large-net (*payang*) fishing gear is modified with a net size of tens or even hundreds of kilometers, using weights, and pulling it using machines instead of human labor. However, the fishing gear is still a matter of debate between the large-net (*payang*) fishermen and the government itself. Both still do not have the same view on fishing gear, where the government considers large-net (*payang*) to be environmentally damaging but fishermen loudly

voice that large-net (*payang*) is environmentally friendly.

Furthermore, movement will never occur without a trigger, the trigger referred to in this case is the factor that causes a movement to occur. It is the same with the movements made by fishermen. Their movement is not for no reason or because of the lure of giving cash and participating in action activities or other lures. The movement carried out by fishermen certainly occurs in several areas in Indonesia, especially among those who feel oppressed or isolated, or disadvantaged by policies issued by the Government (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries). Therefore, this paper wants to discuss more deeply related fishermen's organizations in Lamongan Regency, particularly in terms of formation and movement.

Methods

The research method uses qualitative methods, with a case study approach. Research conducted by exploring research problems by collecting data (text and visual) that reflects participants' views on the research problem being studied is called a qualitative method (Craswell, 2018).

The technique of collecting data through literature review, observation, and interviews. The literature review was conducted by building a theory, and to serve as a basic reference for this research. The data obtained through the literature study is used as a theoretical basis that serves as a guideline in conducting this research. The observation was conducted by conducting a site survey of Lamongan Regency for two weeks where the research team was at the location of Brondong fishing village, Lamongan, East Java. Interviews were conducted with several key informants, including three heads of fishermen organizations, two fisheries entrepreneurs, two fishermen cooperative administrators, and five fishermen.

Data analysis of the results of this research is poured in descriptive writing, which describes the results of research related to fishermen's organizations and formations and movements

carried out based on primary data and secondary data that have been obtained previously.

Results

Formation of Fishermen Organization

Fishermen organizations have different functions depending on their scope and objectives. Some organizations focus on ensuring sustainable harvesting of fisheries resources by regulating fishing activities and setting quotas (Pintassilgo et al., 2008), while others aim to protect the rights, strengthen the socio-economic standing, and improve the welfare of fisher members (Hapsari et al., 2020; Lestari, 2019; Manulu, 2016). Fishermen organizations can also function in the prevention of illegal fishermen, non-reporting fishermen, and unregulated fishermen, which refers to fishermen activities that do not comply with or contradict the management or conservation measures applicable to a particular fishery (Latun et al., 2013). Illegal fishing activities are included as criminal offenses for transnational crimes (Mubarok, 2019). In addition, fisher organizations have an impact on sustainable development (Loera & Zulawska, 2013). Fishermen organizations can work with governments and local communities to promote sustainable fishing practices by enhancing economic, social, and environmental development in the region, reducing harvesting capacity in fisheries, preventing significant adverse impacts to vulnerable marine ecosystems, estimating fishing activities from vessel monitoring systems (VMS), and developing legal measures to control illegal fishing by non-reporting and unruly fishers.

Fishermen's organizations can also conduct fishermen's movements in order to create sustainable development (Suwarno, 2016). Fishermen organizations can provide a platform to coordinate efforts, strengthen solidarity among fishermen, and provide a collective voice to fight for change. Organizations are essential tools of struggle. Therefore, it is not surprising that organizations are often also closely related to social movements (Hapsari et al., 2020). Social

movements are present as a means of rejecting injustice to ensure survival above the environmental damage that occurs (Suwarno, 2016). Social movements are a more effective alternative in urging changes in public policy when various formal mechanisms and channels are very complicated, lack access, and seem closed (Manulu, 2016).

Organizations for coastal communities are very important to help the problems faced by fishermen. The coast of Lamongan Regency has several community organizations that have functions as controllers, and protectors and also assist fishermen in Lamongan Regency. The organization does not only focus on one fishing community but also all fishermen in the fishing area. In this discussion, the organizations presented are organizations involved in large-net (*payang*) fishermen.

First, the All Indonesian Fishermen Association (*Himpunan Nelayan Seluruh Indonesia* or HNSI) in Lamongan Regency has existed since 1996, but at that time it was not named HNSI and is still not as effective as it is today. HNSI itself was born on May 21, 1973, as a process of the historical development of the movement of Indonesian fishermen, which was marked by the unification of all fishing organizations that existed at that time. HNSI as a professional and non-governmental organization, is an educational arena for fishermen and training for fishermen and coastal communities, to develop mental attitudes and thinking patterns, as well as to increase their knowledge and skills in carrying out marine and fishery development in order to increase income, the standard of living, and his welfare.

As a functional organization, HNSI is a mode to increase the participation of fishermen and coastal communities in the success of marine and fisheries development; a connecting bridge to solve problems that arise between fishermen, or fishermen with the government or with certain parties; means as a place to channel the aspirations of the fishing community in national or international forums. In line with what the chairman of the HNSI of Lamongan Regency Mr. S said that HNSI Lamongan is a forum to

accommodate the aspirations of the fishing community in Lamongan Regency (Interview Document, 2018).

As an independent and non-participating organization, HNSI is an independent organization, not an under any political organization, does not depend on anyone, is not affiliated and keeps a distance from all political parties in Indonesia, and ends together and works together with all components of the nation in the context of realizing a just and prosperous Indonesian society, physically and mentally prosperous, independent, becoming a superior nation and having high competitiveness in the international world. This was also expressed by the chairman of the Lamongan HNSI in the interview session, Mr. S said "HNSI Lamongan is not affiliated with any political party, we do not want to be involved in the world of politics" (*Interview Document*).

Second, The Indonesian Fishermen Alliance (*Aliansi Nelayan Indonesia – ANI*), chaired by Mr. Agus Mulyono, is a non-governmental organization that was only established in 2017. The organization was established because the HNSI attribute used during the action was not allowed, thus the large-net (*payang*) Fishermen's Alliance throughout Indonesia emerged. Agus Mulyono as chairman of ANI previously served as chairman of the Lamongan branch of HNSI.

Third, The Lamongan Fish Entrepreneurs Association (*Asosiasi Pengusaha Ikan Lamongan - ASPILA*) is an organization comprised of fish entrepreneurs. This organization also has a great influence on the fishing community, where these fish entrepreneurs buy fish from the fishermen's catch.

Fourth, Village Unit Cooperative (*Koperasi Unit Desa - KUD*) "*Minatani*" is a cooperative located in Brondong, Lamongan Regency, and is now a national model cooperative because it is able to empower the economy of fishermen and farmers. KUD "*Minatani*" itself handles several business units such as the production of hand-rolled clove cigarettes (*sigaret kretek tangan - SKT*) through a partnership with *PT HM Sampoerna Tbk*, ice block production, cold storage, savings, and loans. The cooperative has more than 1,000

members consisting of fishermen and farmers. The fishermen's need for ice blocks is very high, usually spending 20,000 ice blocks per day which is then provided by KUD "Minatani".

In general, fishermen cooperatives are organizations formed by fishermen to improve their economic, social, and ecological conditions (Loera & Zulawska, 2013) with the aim of promoting sustainable development in the region together with the government and the community, while fishermen associations are organizations that represent the interests and needs of fishermen in a region or community to protect the rights, strengthening the socio-economic position, and improving the welfare of fishermen members.

And the last, The large-net (*payang*) Association was officially established on August 24, 2018. This association is more focused on paying attention to issues related to large-net (*payang*). Its location is in Brondong Village, Lamongan Regency.

Fishermen's associations can provide services such as fish marketing and processing, as well as training and education for fishermen (Yoshikuni, 2005). Fishermen associations can also serve as a medium for fishermen to voice their concerns and advocate for policies that benefit fishermen.

Movements of Fisherman Organization

[Social] movements among fishermen in Indonesia became more frequent after the end of the New Order era (Hapsari, et al., 2020). This was due to the degradation of marine resources and the environment, as well as the poverty of fishermen during the New Order (Kingseng,

2017). The Fishermen's Social Movement often emerges in response to issues faced by fishing communities, such as declining fish catches (Pathurrahman, Hadiyanor, Hairini, & Tabitha, 2022), reduced access to fisheries resources (Tiro, Irianti, & Wardani, 2023), unfair exploitation in the fish supply chain, or policy changes that disadvantage fishers (Hapsari, et al., 2020). The fishermen's social movement begins with increased awareness among fishermen about the issues they face and the consequences to their lives (Lestari, 2019). This awareness then triggers mobilization and generates enthusiasm to organize themselves, share experiences, and work together to achieve change. Finally, fisher social movements often involve the formation of fisher organizations or associations that aim to protect and fight for the interests of fishermen.

Movement will never occur without a trigger, the trigger means in this case is the cause or factor that causes a movement to occur. It is the same with the movement carried out by fishermen. Their movement is not without a cause or because of the lure of giving cash and participating in action activities or other lures. Movements carried out by fishermen certainly occur in several regions in Indonesia, especially those who feel oppressed or isolated, or harmed by policies issued by the Government.

The results of the analysis of policy documents indicate that there are several things that can indeed be detrimental or suffocating which even want to alienate the community from the fishing gear that has been the life support of the fishing community. The following are the contents or important points of these policies.

Table 1. Policy Documents that Potentially Disadvantage Fishermen

Regulation	Explanations
Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Regulation No. 02/Permen-KP/2015 (Prohibition Of The Use Of Trawls And Sine Nets)	Article 2: Every person is prohibited from using trawls and seine nets in all Fisheries Management Areas of the Republic of Indonesia. Article 4, Paragraph (2): Boat or vessel seines as referred to in Paragraph (1) letter b consist of: a) <i>Dogol</i> (danis hseines); b) Scottish seines; c) Pair seines; d) <i>Payang</i> ; e) <i>Cantrang</i> ; and

	f) <i>Basic lampara</i>
Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Regulation No. 71/Permen-KP/2016. (Fish Passages and Fishing Gear Placement)	<p>Chapter V, Disruptive and destructive fishing gear. Article 21 paragraph (1) Fishing gear that interferes with and damages the sustainability of fish resources is fishing gear that is operated: a) Threatens the extinction of biota; b) Results in habitat destruction; and c) Endangers the safety of users.</p> <p>Paragraph (2) APIs that interfere with and damage the sustainability of fish resources as referred to in paragraph (1), consist of:</p> <p>a) Seine nets, which include Dogol (Danish seines), Scottish seines, Pair seines, <i>Payang</i>, and Basic <i>Lampara</i>;</p> <p>b) Trawls, which include Bottom trawls, Beam trawls, Otter trawls, Pair trawls, Nephrops trawls, Shrimp trawls, Shrimp trawls, Midwater trawls, Otter trawls, Fish trawls, Pair trawls, Shrimp trawls, and Ottertwin trawls; and</p> <p>c) Traps, which include Aerial traps and Muroami.</p> <p>Paragraph (3) API arrangements that interfere with and damage the sustainability of fish resources as referred to in paragraph (1) are prohibited from being operated on all fishing lines in all WPPNRI as listed in the appendix which is an integral part of this ministerial regulation.</p>
Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Regulation No. 72/Permen-KP/2016. (Requirements And Procedures For Issuing Certificate Of Management Feasibility)	<p>Chapter II Scope, Article 2 Includes 1. Issuance of Certification of Processing Feasibility (SKP);</p> <p>2. Requirements and Procedures for issuing SKP; 3. Quality Control; and 4. Coaching</p>
Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Regulation No. 01/Permen-kp/2017 (Fishery Vessel Operation License)	<p>Chapter 1, general provisions article 1 consists of:</p> <p>1. Fishery Vessel Operation License (<i>Surat Laik Operasi Kapal Perikanan /SLO</i>) is a certificate stating that a fishery vessel has fulfilled the administrative requirements and technical feasibility to conduct fishery activities.</p> <p>2. Fishing License, (<i>Surat Izin Penangkapan Ikan /SIPI</i>), is a written permit that must be owned by every fishing vessel to carry out fishing activities which is an integral part of the Fisheries Business License (SIUP).</p> <p>3. Fish Transportation Vessel License (<i>Surat Izin Kapal Pengangkut Ikan /SIKPI</i>) is a written permit that must be owned by every fishing vessel to carry out fish transportation activities.</p> <p>4. Transmitter Activation Certificate (<i>Surat Keterangan Aktivasi Transmitter /SKAT</i>) is a written document stating that the transmitter of the online Fishery Vessel Monitoring System (SPKP) on a particular fishing vessel has been installed, activated, and can be monitored at the fishery vessel monitoring center.</p> <p>5. Minutes of Ship Inspection Results (<i>Berita Acara Hasil Pemeriksaan Kapal /BA-HPK</i>) is a form that contains the results of the examination of administrative requirements and technical feasibility of fishery vessels as the basis for issuing a Fishery Vessel Operation License (SLO).</p>

The content of the policy is only part of the overall content, pieces taken based on the informant's statements during interviews. Because the points of the regulation are considered very troublesome or undermine the time and energy of fishermen and even threaten their survival. In line with what was said by D who said that: "*actually what strangles fishermen is the regulation of the minister of fisheries and marine affairs*". Based on these various fisheries policies, the Lamongan community then questioned the

president's promise to make Indonesia a maritime axis. Informants A, D, and N agreed to explain that:

"that the president's promise to make Indonesia a maritime axis was a mere hoax so that the fishing community as a whole voted for him during the presidential election yesterday. The community was deceived as evidenced by the policy of the Ministry of Maritime Affairs. We are sure that the one who ordered it was a superior or at least the superior

must have known about the policy." (Interview document)

The Lamongan coastal community as a whole is an activity related to fishermen. Therefore, between one job and another are interrelated, and the activity of fishing or catching fish using large-net (*payang*) fishing gear (prohibited by the government) is still widely used in the coastal area. Where the catch then falls into the hands of traders and then sold again by the community, the activity of sorting fish which is also the most important part, and besides that, transportation activities that transport people in activities to the Fish Sales Place (TPI) are all interrelated with each other. In line with what was said by a fisherman with the initials D. said that:

"all the work that exists in this place is a unity or interrelated and cannot be separated and the main axis of the entire work relationship is fishing with large-net (payang) " (Interview document)

The movement that occurred was a response to the policy that was later issued by the Ministry of Maritime Affairs which was contained in the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Regulation No. 01/2017, No. 02/2015, No. 71/2016, and No. 72/2016. In general, the regulation contains a ban on the use of trawls or often known as *large-net (payang)* for the Lamongan area, and also various licenses that are considered too complicated.

With this view of the community, it will give birth to a very tight resistance among the fishing community. The struggle of the movement will certainly be very dialectical and also full of interests, of course, but what happens in the Lamongan community is a movement that is truly pure for the interests of the fishing community in the coastal areas of Lamongan Regency.

Of course, the prohibition of the use of large-net (*payang*) by the relevant ministry is considered by the Lamongan community to be paralyzing the fishing community, which has been using the fishing gear for generations. The Lamongan community claims that the large-net (*payang*) that they use does not damage the environment and is environmentally friendly, so this is what

actually triggers the fishing community movement that occurs in the Lamongan area and Indonesia in general.

The movement of the fishing community achieved positive results because in the end after the turmoil of various movements in several regions and at the center, the government in this case the President of Indonesia Mr. Jokowi in his speech said that "please reopen the fishermen in an unspecified time". Of course, this makes fishermen incomparably happy. However, they did not dissolve in pleasure because the minister's policy has not been revoked or revised by the government until now. This has led to concerns from the community because they see different policies between the president and his ministers.

Discussion

Fishermen organizations have great potential to influence social change in their environment. This is because fisher organizations are an important part of socially and economically vulnerable coastal communities. The fishermen's social movement itself emerged due to social and ecological problems caused by state-companies (Alkhudri, Dharmawan, & Kingseng, 2018). In addition, a movement arises because of the conflict between the community and the political elite against the rules made (Lestari, 2019). Viewed genealogically, the fishermen's movement metamorphoses in the organization, problem, and scale of the movement (Hapsari, et al., 2020). The fishermen's movement is a collective effort by fishing communities to achieve significant social change related to issues that affect their lives and livelihoods.

Fishermen movements can involve advocacy campaigns that aim to change policies, improve working conditions, or protect the rights of fishermen (Hapsari, et al., 2020). This can involve demonstrations, public meetings, dialogue with stakeholders, or legal action to fight for the movement's goals. Broadly speaking, social movements are divided into two: bottom-up actor mobilization theory and top-down social movement phenomena (Sztompka,

2014). The bottom-up actor mobilization theory is dominant in the current era because the actors involved include: people, clerics, or grass-roots. The characteristics of the movement are sporadic, partial, not systemic, and not supported by a strong ideology (pseudo-populism heavy) (Pathurrahman, Hadiyanor, Hairini, & Tabitha, 2022) (Hapsari, et al., 2020). In contrast, the top-down movement actor theory is filled by the nobility, ulama (religious leaders), and *jawara* (community leaders) because it is determined by structural conditions that provide them with political opportunities.

The movement at the local level, especially in the Lamongan Regency, emerged as a result of a previous cause, namely the birth of the Ministry

of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs policy which was considered impartial to the fishing communities in the Indonesian region. The existence of the policy indeed gave birth to a polemic that shook the fishing community, why not, fishing gear that has long been used by fishermen is then claimed by the government as fishing gear that damages the environment and threatens the sustainability of fish. A fisherman with the initials S said that:

"This fishing gear is a fishing gear that we have used for generations, from the past until now, if it is damaging why is it only now being prohibited. This means that there may be interests from the government?" (Interview document).

Figure 2. The Lamongan Fishermen's Movement.
Source: A fisherman Documentation

The Lamongan fishermen's movement is a very clean movement that has not been injured by various practical political mounts from a certain party or the lure of money or other things that can harm the Lamongan community movement. A fisherman with the initials A said that:

"We are doing this movement purely not because of the lure of money from certain parties and not the lure of political parties, but instead the government coalition parties support the movement we are doing because this is related to many people,

especially the various jobs of fishermen and those related to fishermen?" (Interview document).

Based on the previous explanation, it appears that the Lamongan coastal community in carrying out the movement has not been contaminated by the interests of outsiders who want to take advantage of the large-net (*payang*) polemic. In addition, the community's awareness of the need for representation in the government has encouraged them to propose the House of Representatives of the People of Indonesia

(DPR) candidate for the 2019 election. Informants D and A were more emphatic in their statements:

"We are aware that the policies made by the minister of marine affairs and fisheries are smooth and smooth in the central government due to the absence of fishermen representatives who represent us, so the government arbitrarily carries out various intimidations against fishing communities with various policies that are only for the benefit of the government" (interview document).

In the end, the fishermen's movement in coastal Lamongan can be said to be a fishermen's movement that is still far from outside contamination. In addition, the Lamongan fishermen community also once expelled a ceremonial activity conducted by the Ministry of Maritime Affairs which took place at the new Lamongan Fish Landing Place (TPI). The activity was an activity of giving fishing gear that was not intended for fishermen around the Fish Landing Place (TPI), so the surrounding community as homeowners felt offended and immediately gathered members to come one by one, which in the end the government and its fishing gear were removed from the Fish Landing Place (TPI) area and this was confirmed by all informants we asked at the location. They think that the government deliberately wants to do the ceremonial acceptance at our location because they want to make us a benchmark if we do not fight back then they will conclude that all other fishermen will be safe because, in fact, it is the Lamongan fishing community that is very loudly opposing the policy of the minister of marine and fisheries.

Conclusion

Based on the data analysis that has been presented previously, several conclusions can be drawn:

First, Lamongan coastal fishermen have been using large-net (*payang*) fishing gear for generations. According to their perception, this fishing gear is environmentally friendly. They also prove this belief in environmental friendliness by challenging the government to

conduct a sampling test on the fishing gear used by fishermen in the Lamongan region.

Second, the organization of the fishermen's movement in the Lamongan Regency was formed bottom-up as a form of resistance to the issuance of government policies, in this case, the Regulation of the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries which prohibits the use of large-net (*payang*) fishing gear which has the potential to damage the environment.

Third, the organization of the movement is carried out by involving various organizations that have been previously formed independently with driving actors who have long been involved in fishermen's organizations. This driving actor made alliances with various existing fishermen's organizations such as The Indonesian Fishermen Association (HNSI), The Indonesian Fishermen Alliance (ANI), The Lamongan Fish Entrepreneurs Association (ASPILA), and The Lamongan large-net (*payang*) Association.

And finally, the successful fishermen's movement against the Minister of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs' policy on the prohibition of large-net (*payang*) is considered successful with the issuance of a presidential instruction that provides a moratorium on the ban until an unspecified time limit. This success has been welcomed by the return of Lamongan fishermen to the sea.

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